

Improving Intrusion Detection Accuracy using Convolution Neural Network

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Abstract: Network Intrusion Detection has been an active area of research with the growing incidences of cybercrimes. This has led to continuous monitoring of network traffic, analysis, and raise alarm if any abnormality is noticed so as to trigger appropriate response in order to curb the possibility of an attack. One of the approaches to deal with the network intrusion problem is to classify the network user behavior as normal or suspicious. Soft computing based techniques are being tried out to classify network users with higher degree of accuracy and low false alarm rate. In this paper, we propose a classification model for the detection of known as well as unknown network attacks based on artificial neural network based techniques namely, RBFN, SOM, LVQ3, SMO, and CNN. Further, in order to improve the performance of the classifier, Z-Score normalization has been applied for preprocessing of data. The performance of the model has been evaluated on the NSL-KDD dataset in terms of Precision, Accuracy, Detection rate, F-Value, and False Alarm rate.

Keywords: Convolution Neural Network, Learning Vector Quantization, Normalization, Self-Organizing Map, Sequential Minimal Optimization, and Radial Basis Function Network.

I. Introduction

Increasing number of internet based applications has raised security concerns due to hackers and network intruders. Intruders are engaging themselves in different illegal activities such as cracking, guessing passwords, viewing sensitive data without authorization, logging into workstations without

permission. Online applications in the financial sector, military services, online markets are the most vulnerable ones which require immediate attention. Maintaining confidentiality, integrity, availability and protection of data against security threats has always been a challenge. As cyber-attacks are becoming more sophisticated day-by-day, it has become a real challenge to identify unknown attacks. Security threats such as zero-day attacks have notoriously effected internet users. Many countries have been significantly impacted by the zero-day attacks. As per the Symantec Internet Security threat report [1] there were more than three billion zero-day attacks in 2016. There are three class of intruders [2] namely, Masquerader: unauthorized user who penetrates a system's access controls to exploit a legitimate user's account, Misfeasor: a legitimate user who attempts for an unauthorized access or misuse his/her privileges, and Clandestine user: who captures supervisory control to dodge auditing and access controls or suppress system audit data. It is observed that preventive measures such as firewalls, spyware, cryptography, virtual private networks are becoming less effective. Thus, the design of an intelligent IDS is a challenging task. An IDS can be classified into host-based (HIDS) and network-based (NIDS) detection systems [3]. HIDS monitors the hosts and analyses the host information such as system calls and log files. NIDS monitors network traffic and raise an alarm if it discovers any suspicious or potential malicious activity or known threats are found. Soft computing provides the ability to build computationally intelligent systems that mimics human capabilities to learn and reason from imprecise and uncertain environments [4].

Soft computing encompasses many computing paradigms, including fuzzy sets, simulated annealing, neural networks, genetic algorithms, approximate reasoning, etc.

Various soft computing approaches have been tried in the area of intrusion detection [5, 6]. Neural network based IDS models have the ability to differentiate between normal and suspicious activities of a system. In this work, a novel IDS based on neural network classifiers is described. [7] analyzed neurotree classifier which is a hybridization of neural network and decision tree. Further, wrapper approach feature selection method has been applied on the dataset to select important features. [8] proposed a rule based approach using enhanced C4.5 algorithm for detection of abnormal behavior of internal attackers. An effective model has been developed [9] using info gain feature selection method to select important features and c4.5 classification techniques. [10] have proposed a multi-level hybrid IDS that uses SVM and modified K-means algorithm. KDD CUP 99 dataset is used to analyze the performance of the model. An effective intrusion detection model has been proposed [11] based on support vector machine. On experimenting with NSL-KDD dataset, the result shows improved performance in terms of detection rate, accuracy, and low false alarm rate. [12] applied principle component analysis and information gain for feature reduction on dataset and tested against ensemble of SVM, K-nearest neighbor and multilayer perceptron classifiers.

II. Methodology

The objective of the proposed model as depicted in fig. 1 is to build an effective intrusion detection system with high recall value and low false positive rate. The proposed model for the Neural Network based IDS comprises of two layers. In the first layer the NSL-KDD dataset attribute values are standardized using Z-score normalization. Next, the normalized dataset is classified using five neural network based techniques namely, RBFN, SOM, LVQ3, SMO, and CNN as explained in the following subsections.

Fig.1 Proposed Model

A. Radial Basis Function Network (RBFN)

Radial basis function network [13] is a feed forward neural network with three distinct layers namely, input layer (first layer), hidden layer (second layer) and output layer (last layer). The input layer contains the source nodes whose number is equal to the dimension of the input vector. The hidden layer consists of a number of nodes that performs a nonlinear transformation of the input variables using Gaussian function. The output layer is a summation unit. RBF network has two phases: In the first phase, the centers of the hidden layer nodes are determined using k-means clustering, and in the second phase the connection weights are computed using linear regression.

Fig. 2: Architecture of a Radial Basis Function Network

B. Self-Organizing Map (SOM)

The self-organizing feature map is an unsupervised artificial neural network model that is based on Kohonen's discovery [14]. Kohonen's self-organizing neural networks in the principle of winner-takes all. The network has two layers of processing units namely, an input layer and an output layer. There are no hidden layers. It is assumed that the output or cluster units are arranged in one or two dimensional arrays. Learning takes place with the help of a given set of patterns and the given number of clusters into which the patterns are to be clustered. Initially the clusters are unknown, i.e., knowledge about the patterns that form a particular cluster or the cluster to which a pattern belongs is absent at the beginning. During the clustering process, the network organizes itself gradually and form a cluster. During training, the cluster unit whose weight vector is closest to the given input pattern is the winner. Next, the weight vectors of all cluster units in the neighborhood of the winner are updated.

C. LVQ3

LVQ3 [15] is a supervised learning process where two code-book vectors p_q and p_r , which represent two nearest neighbors of y , are simultaneously updated, where y and p_r belong to the same class and y and p_q belong to different classes. Moreover, y must fall into a zone of values called the "window", which is defined around the mid-plane of p_q and p_r . Assuming that d_q and d_r are the Euclidean distances of y from p_q and p_r respectively, then y falls in a window of relative width w , if

$$\text{Min} \left(\frac{dq}{dr}, \frac{dr}{dq} \right) > \left(\frac{1-w}{1+w} \right)$$

The rules for updating p_q and p_r ensure that the code-book vectors continue to approximate the respective class distributions, and improve the quality of the classification boundary.

These rules are:

$$p_q(t+1) = p_q(t) - \beta(t)[y(t) - p_q(t)] \quad \text{and}$$

$$p_r(t+1) = p_r(t) - \beta(t)[y(t) - p_r(t)]$$

If y , p_q and p_r belong to the same class, then the code-book vectors are adjusted as follows to improve upon:

$$p_s(t+1) = p_s(t) - \varepsilon(t)\beta(t)[y(t) - p_s(t)]$$

where t is the discretized time index, $\beta(t)$ is the learning rate, and $\varepsilon(t)$ is the relative learning rate.

D. Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO)

The Sequential Minimal Optimization [16] is an efficient algorithm and can quickly solve the SVM QP problem without any need for storing a huge matrix and can skip the numerical QP optimization steps. SMO decomposes the large QP problem into a series of smallest possible QP problems. These small QP problems are solved analytically. The amount of memory required for SMO is linear in the training set size, thereby, allowing SMO to handle very large training data sets. For the standard SVM QP problem, the smallest possible optimization problem involves two Lagrange multipliers. The SMO algorithm is composed of three parts:

- One heuristic to choose the first Lagrange multiplier
- Another heuristic to choose the second Lagrange multiplier
- The code to solve the optimization problem analytically for the two chosen multipliers

E. Convolution Neural Network (CNN)

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) were originally proposed by LeCun to derive and analyze the feature set of the input data [17]. CNN are the regularized version of MLP where each layer consists of a partially connected layer (Conv1D), Pooling layer, and a Dropout layer (to avoid overfitting). Each layer of CNN can consist of many convolution kernels that are used to generate different feature maps. Some of the Neurons of a CNN layer are connected to the subsequent layers to pass on information to extract features.

The model starts with a Conv1D layer which has 64 nodes with a stride size of 3. The layer is activated with ReLU activation function. The ReLU function returns 0 if the input is negative and returns the input when it is positive. Next, a MaxPooling 1D layer is applied with a stride size of 3 which computes the maximum of all the values for each slide range to reduce overfitting. The model continues with another set of Conv1D and MaxPooling layers.

To improve recognition of longer sequences in the data, LSTM layers are included. LSTMs have been designed to avoid long-term dependency problem.

Dropout is a regularization method, which approximates training a large number of neural networks with different architectures concurrently in order to decrease overfitting of

data. During the training process, some number of layer outputs are dropped. This has the effect of making the layer look-like and be treated-like a layer with a different number of nodes and connectivity to the prior layer. This leads to each layer viewing a different version of the information it originally received, i.e. different view of the configured input. Dropping temporarily ignores a part of data and presents a different version that it initially receives. This makes the training process noisy, forcing nodes within a layer to probabilistically take on more/less responsible for the inputs. This layer drops 10% of the outputs.

Another set of LSTM and Dropout layers are added to the model to gain insights from the previous LSTM layers and look for further patterns.

Finally, a fully connected layer or Dense layer is added which has 5 nodes to account for the four types of attacks and no

attack instance. The output from this layer gives the probability of each attack to have occurred.

III. Experimental Setup

A. NSL-KDD Dataset

In this study publicly available online NSL-KDD dataset [18] is used for evaluating the efficiency of different classifiers. The dataset contains 1,25,973 connections for training and testing. It includes 41 features and a class label which indicates whether or not the data record represents a normal scenario or one of the four different attack types, such as DOS (Denial of Service), R2L (Remote to Local), Probes, and U2R (User to Root).

Fig. 3: CNN Model

B. Preprocessing

Normalization is required when the attributes are on drastically different scales. Normalization is particularly useful for classification algorithms involving neural networks or distance measurements such as nearest neighbor classification and clustering. In this work neural network based techniques are applied on NSL-KDD dataset for performance analysis. NSL-KDD dataset consists of multiple attributes and the attributes have values on different scales. Normalization techniques such as Z-Score (also called as Standard score) normalization, Min-Max normalization, Normalization by Decimal scaling are being commonly used. Here, we have used Z-Score Normalization [19] for pre-processing of the dataset. Z-score normalization is calculated using the formula:

$$Z = (x - \mu) / \sigma$$

where μ is the mean of the population

σ is the standard deviation of the population

x is the raw score

C. Test Mode

In this work, two types of test modes are applied namely, percentage split (75% train and 25% test) and 10-fold cross-validation. In percentage split mode the entire dataset is randomly divided into training set and test set. Here, 75% data records are used for building the training model and its effectiveness is tested on 25% data records. In 10-fold cross-validation, all the records of the dataset are randomly partitioned into 10 equal subsets. Next, out of 10 subsets one particular subset is used for testing purpose and other 9 subsets are used as training data. The process is repeated 10 times, and accuracy of the classifier is determined by taking an average over 10 runs.

D. Performance Measurement

Here, a confusion matrix is used to measure the performance of different classifiers in terms of precision, accuracy, recall value (or detection rate), F-value, and false alarm rate. The confusion matrix [19] analyzes how well the classification techniques recognize tuples of different classes. For P class of tuples, confusion matrix is a table of $P \times P$ matrix. The matrix reports number of True Positives, False Positives, True Negatives and False Negatives.

True Positive: Positive tuples that were correctly labeled by the classifier.

False Positive: Negative tuples that were incorrectly labeled

True Negative: Negative tuples that were correctly labeled by the classifier

False Negative: Positive tuples that were incorrectly labeled by the classifier

The performance of the model is measured using precision, accuracy, recall / detection rate, and false alarm rate.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TN+TP+FN+FP}$$

$$\text{Detection Rate or Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

$$F - \text{Value} = 2 * \frac{(\text{Precision} * \text{Recall})}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})}$$

$$\text{False Alarm Rate (FAR)} = \frac{FP}{TN+FP}$$

IV. Results and Discussion

Table 1 depicts the performance of five neural network based classification techniques. The performance of different techniques is evaluated on the basis of precision, accuracy, recall, F-Value, and false alarm rate. 10-fold cross-validation and percent split (75% Train and 25% test) have been used for training and testing. The result shows that convolution neural network gives highest accuracy, highest detection rate and very lowest false alarm rate irrespective of the test mode. This suggests that the CNN classification outperforms other techniques. A comparative analysis with other known approaches is also presented in Table 2.

Table: 1 Comparison of Neural Network based Classifiers

Classifier Techniques	Test Mode	Evaluation Criteria				
		Precision in %	Accuracy in %	Recall in %	F-Value in %	False Alarm Rate in %
RBFN	10-Fold Cross-Validation	87.6381	91.1576	94.3033	90.8486	11.581
	Percent Split (75% Train)	94.1673	92.2745	88.9412	91.4796	4.8132
SOM	10-Fold Cross-Validation	94.1973	94.2829	93.4743	93.8344	5.0131
	Percent Split (75% Train)	95.6503	94.2273	91.7943	93.6827	3.6471
LVQ3	10-Fold Cross-Validation	96.8938	91.8554	85.2328	90.69	2.3789
	Percent Split (75% Train)	90.6991	87.829	82.3425	86.319	7.3774
SMO	10-Fold Cross-Validation	98.7632	98.3401	97.6565	98.2067	1.0647
	Percent Split (75% Train)	98.7683	98.3806	97.746	98.2545	1.065
CNN	10-Fold Cross-Validation	99.7549	99.6634	99.5244	99.6395	0.2146
	Percent Split (75% Train)	99.1941	99.3935	99.5109	99.3522	0.7094

Table 2: A Comparative Analysis

Author	Feature Selection Method	Classifiers	Accuracy	Recall/Detection Rate	False Alarm Rate
[20]	Best First Search	Ctree	Not provided	99.33%	15.7%
		FRIDS	Not provided	95.98%	12.63%
		EIFRID	Not provided	98.89%	5.03%
[21]	Rough set	SVM	89.13%	86.72%	13.27%
[22]	Best First Search	AIRS1	94.2757%	90.6549%	2.5719%
[23]	Rough set	Neural Network with Indicator Variable	Not Provided	96.7%	3%
[10]		SVM and modified K-Means	95.75%	Not provided	Not provided
[24]	Genetic Search	Naïve Bayes	Not Provided	95.9963%	Not Provided
[25]	Ensemble method	OS-LEM	Not Provided	97.67%	1.74%
[26]	Chi-square	SVM (Multiclass)	98%	Not provided	Not provided
Present Work	Z-Score Normalization (Standardization)	CNN	99.6634	99.5244	0.2146

Fig.4 Comparison of Accuracy

Fig.5 Comparison of Detection Rate

Fig.6 Comparison of FAR

V. Conclusion

Building efficient intrusion detection models is a challenging task. In this paper the analysis is based on different neural network based classification with Z-score normalization. The performances of the classifiers have been evaluated on the basis of precision, accuracy, detection rate, F-Value, and false alarm rate. It is observed that the Convolution Neural Network classifier gives highest accuracy, highest detection rate and lowest false alarm rate irrespective of the test method employed.

VI. Future Scope

In this work, we have applied some of the potential neural network based techniques for the classification of intrusion data. In future, we would like to continue our work by exploring other machine learning techniques. Our sole objective is to enhance the detection accuracy and reduce false positives as far as possible. Therefore, in order to further increase the performance of the classification models we would like to improvise the preprocessing phase through effective feature selection.

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